

Riemann Hypothesis. This is why it is true. (Other helps to those interested verify)

Dante Servi

This revision equals to a deletion.
Instead I want to point out two of my preprints on the same topic.

Riemann's Hypothesis. This is why it is true.
Traces of the Riemann zeta function on the complex plane.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6654333>
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026759>

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